

Research Article

Mini Anchovies Peeler

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Abstract: *The industrial sector is one of the important sectors in Malaysia in this decade. This can be seen through its contribution in generating national income. Hence, various approaches are used and have been made to achieve goals from developing countries to developed countries. One of the goals towards a developed country is to ensure that Malaysia is one of the most innovative country. Therefore, the basis of the study is done on an important element in the economic aspect and the ability of this study is also a descriptive study. This study focuses on the performance evaluation analysis of the pepper seed separation process through the developed product model. The product model called Mini Anchovies Peeler was generated after getting an idea from the problems obtained and from a survey of several housewives and street foods seller. Data are collected and evaluated to determine the necessary parameters used in model development. Objective of this product was to solve the source of the problem. Three aspects of the main problems have been identified and the solution of the three main problems, which is to simplify the work of peel anchovies, separating fish guts and energy saving are selected for analysis. The quantity and quality of processing for the workstation, the number of resources and the time taken for the user to complete one process cycle were taken. Mini Anchovies Peeler successfully increases the quantity and quality of work separation compared to existing manual work procedures. Mini Anchovies Peeler also successfully reduces the time of 40% of the existing work for processing 100 grams of dry peppers. In general, this product can help simplify kitchen work in separating fish guts and help produce the maximum quantity for those who running business. At the same time, saving working time can be achieved and reduce energy.*

Keywords: Mini Anchovies Peeler; Fish guts

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, in this modern era of technologies, manufacturing environment becomes highly competitive. Many companies have made a resolution to become a world class manufacturer. Continual improvement in quality, lower scrap, shorter lead time, reducing bottleneck, lower machine cycle time and others will be done to maximized the productivity (Glenny and Mac kulak, 1985).

The manufacture of domestic products that are more efficient in design, more work problems can be solved and increased work force, cost reduction and guarantee quality and quantity results. It is fulfilling Malaysian government's goal to achieve the status of a developed country by 2030.

Rapid development in the fields of science and technology, socioeconomics and politics is one of the factors that caused the increase in the number of factories in the country as a result of which it has led to the use of more sophisticated equipment and technology in daily life and work. This has changed the system and methods of working and the workplace environment. Therefore, identifying the target group that uses machine technology can be achieved hundred percent. The interaction between humans and machines and the environment has forced us to focus and pay attention to

ergonomic aspects. The focus on Work Station Safety is a major topic in safety and health management at the moment.

According to O borne (1987), ergonomics is one of the important principles in performing a work activity. Company of America, Canada and Japanese concluded ergonomics is known as a human engineering factor because it involves a scientific analysis of human aspects in design. The concept of ergonomics is broad, which covers various aspects such as humans, machines, work fields and work environments.

Therefore, the development of Mini Anchovies Peeler was designed to contribute as follows:

- Increase the level of student knowledge
- Increase the ability level of students
- Identify the time that can be produced in peeling anchovies.
- Reduce time to do tasks.

Mini Anchovies Peeler is one of the household appliances that every family must have. *Mini Anchovies Peeler* is a device to peeler and to separate guts from anchovies. The main advantage of this *Mini Anchovies Peeler* is that it is very compact and easy to use. Usually, these devices are designed for longevity. They should last a long time, efficient, and most importantly, to bring convenience to the cooking process.

Mini Anchovies Peeler is an anchovy peeling machine. This machine can generally help women in preparing food. Especially those who have a career because it can save time and carry out work quickly. This machine is affordable because the manufacturing and usage costs are relatively cheap. Without prolonged electrical use. This machine uses a rechargeable battery.

1.1 Problem Statement

The idea of developing this product arose when seeing the difficulty of preparing stir fried anchovy sauce for cooking our traditional food nasi lemak. After conducting a question and answer survey to several housewives and hawkers, significant findings were found.

1.2 Significance of the Study / Importance of the Study

- Variety size of Anchovies
- Separate guts from fish
- Peeler works more smoothly
- Save time and energy

1.3 Project Objectives

Mini Anchovies Peeler designed to meet several objectives such as:

- a) Facilitation of pepper seed separation work
- b) Labor cost reduction
- c) Saving working time
- d) Protect hand skin from itchy and wound

Domestic problems while doing housework are the main problems of housewives who are used to it. One of them is peeling anchovies. Buying peeled anchovies is one way to solve it but it is still a problem when there are shops that do not sell peeled anchovies and even if there are, the price is quite expensive. Considering this problem, the idea of building a Mini Anchovies Peeler for home use using a rechargeable battery arose.

2. METHODOLOGY, RESULT & DISCUSSION

The implementation method discussed in this chapter aims to obtain the information and data needed to achieve the design objective. It covers the collection of information about design and data.

2.1 Product Design and Details

Figure 1. Diagram of Mini Anchovies Peeler

Figure 2. Flow chart of Mini Anchovies Peeler process

2.2 Material, Tool and Equipment

Table 1. Bill of Material (BOM)

TYPES OF MATERIAL & TOOLS	SIZE OF MATERIAL & TOOLS	QUANTITY
Aluminium plate	50 x 80 x 25mm	2
Aluminium plate	30 x 40mm	1
Aluminium bar	Dia 30 x 60	3
Aluminium sheet	200 x 600 x 3mm	1
End mill (Tool for conventional milling)	Ø 6	1
	Ø 10	2
	Ø 12	2
Motor DC	12V	1
Belting rubber	60mm	2
Screw & nuts	M6	20

Table 2. Equipment uses

TYPES OF EQUIPMENT	QUANTITY
Conventional Milling Machine	2
Conventional Turning machine	1
Drilling machine	1
Measuring Equipment:	
a) Vernier Caliper	1
b) Micrometer	1

2.3 Work Process

The machining process is a process where it will remove parts of the material that are not needed so that the shape or size of the product that is to be produced can be applied in a clearer form. However, it depends on the appropriateness of the process carried out. Examples of machining processes include cutting using various type of machines like Milling and Turning. And after each machining process is completed, testing of the work results must be done to ensure the quality of the work conducted according to the particular specifications.

Figure 3. Type of machine uses

Figure 4. Assemble operation of Mini Anchovies Peeler

2.4 Result

Table 3. Comparison Job for 50gram Anchovy

BIL	SCALE	MANUAL JOB USING HAND	MINI ANCHOVIES PEELER
1	WORK RESULT FINDINGS		
2	TIME TAKEN	10 min without separation fish guts	10 min with separation fish guts
3	PARAMETER MEASURE	Messy	More clean
4	PEELER JOB	Take time to peeling	Faster & smooth
5	SAFETY	Itchy and Wound	Protected

4. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

As a result of the final project that has been carried out, skills can be improved from time to time in several aspects including machining skills and making paperwork and work reports about this final project.

In addition to practical skills, management skills are also improved. As a result, through this final project, the design of the Mini Anchovies Peeler looks attractive, simple and able to meet the specifications that has been set to make it easier for users.

4.1 Novelty

This product was originally generated, designed by myself and developed by my own students at the Machining Manufacturing Technology workshop, ADTEC JTM Pasir Gudang campus.

4.2 Advantages and Commercial Features

This product has a great impact in general on all women especially on housewives and hawkers. This product will separate fish guts faster than compared to peeling anchovy using hand.

The advantages towards society this product can speed up work more efficiently and save more time especially for working women.

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